

Feasibility Study of a Medium Voltage 12 kV, 1 kA, LC DC Circuit Breaker

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Abstract— The paper studies design options for a 12 kV, 1 kA LC DC Circuit Breaker with multiple possible applications in future MV DC systems. The stresses on all main components are analysed under conservative assumptions, and evaluation of their implementation is provided. The ultrafast disconnecter is the key component that is assumed to have 6 break points with 2.5 m/s rod velocity and 2 ms opening time. The peak current stress is obtained on detailed PSCAD simulation model as $I_{cp}=4.7$ kA, with conservative assumptions for protection system. The parallel capacitor is the largest component, with the calculated main parameters $V_{Cs}=18$ kV, $C_s=250$ μ F, and estimated weight of $m=80$ kg. The total energy dissipation is 220 kJ, that can be accommodated with 2 standard 5 kV railway arresters (210 kJ), while C_s takes another 10 kJ. The low-voltage pre-charged film capacitor $C_{ch}=6$ mF, 0.8 kV is of modest weight. It is concluded that the design is feasible with expected competitive performance and cost, relative to the commercial HV DC breakers.

Index Terms—DC Circuit Breakers, DC switchgear, MV DC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medium Voltage DC systems are expected to grow and they have been subject of CIGRE working group C6/B4.37 [1] and major recent studies for business opportunities [2]. The demand for MVDC is driven by several factors:

- Proliferation of renewable energy sources, which generate DC power (photovoltaics, wind energy, fuel cells, wave/tidal energy, ...),
- Wider application of energy storage, like batteries, fuel cells an electrolyzers, redox flow, which are all DC,
- Electrification in various industries.

As MV DC systems grow in size and expand they will need reliable protection and control systems, but also means to connect to other MV, HV and LV systems. It is emerging that key new components for MVDC systems are DC Circuit Breakers and DC/DC converters [1][2][3].

DC Circuit Breakers have been used in railway industry for many years but only at voltage below 3 kV. Although standardized and with long experience, these DC CB technologies utilise arc extension/splitting to build up counter

voltage, which cannot be scaled for higher DC voltages. Also, their operating time is too long (10-100 ms) for applications at medium voltage DC networks [1][2].

In the last 15 years, there has been significant research on developing DC Circuit breakers for high voltage applications [3]. In 2021 Zhangbei DC grid project was commissioned which includes 16 DC CBs rated at 525 kV, 25 kA [4][5]. The DC CB technologies adopted at HV levels can be grouped into hybrid [6] and mechanical [7],[8], and both have been implemented in practice.

There has been no practical installation of MV DC CBs except in railway industry. Although, medium voltage systems will have some different requirements, there has been very few design studied of a MV DC CB. VARC DC CB [8] is available at MVDC and HVDC, but it requires internal converter with cost implications and opening time is at least 3 ms.

LC DC CB has been proposed recently as new technology potentially suitable for MV and HV applications [9]. It has been demonstrated as a 5 kV, 2 kA hardware in university laboratory [10]. This is essentially mechanical DC CB and therefore costs are expected to be competitive, while also it is capable of very fast operation which is comparable with faster hybrid DC CBs.

This paper presents the initial study of designing LC DC CB for a typical MV application at 12 kV, with nominal current of 1 kA. The aim is to evaluate technology feasibility and determine stresses and ratings for key components. The initial component selection will be described. A full PSCAD model will be developed, and the model will be used to analyse DC CB responses and dimensioning of various components.

II. LC DC CB TOPOLOGY

Figure 1. shows the LC DC CB with pre-charged capacitor [10], and integrated into a simple DC fault test circuit. This DC CB consists of the following key components:

- Ultrafast disconnecter (S_1),
- Main Capacitor (C_s),
- Pre-charged capacitor (C_h), with trigger (T_1 and D_1), and charging circuit,

- Energy absorber (SA_{Cs})
- Residual breaker (S_2),

The series inductor L_{dc} , will always be used with DC CBs to limit current slope [11], but it may not be consider part of DC CB as it is essential component of DC protection system.

The speed of operation is crucially dependent on the characteristics of Ultrafast Disconnecter (UFD). However, while hybrid DC CBs commutate current at the end of UFD stroke, LC DC CB is able to commutate earlier., i.e. at the beginning of the UFD stroke [9]. This means that fault current can be transferred to parallel capacitor C_s in less than 1 ms after the trip signal, and once C_s is inserted in series in the fault current path it enables rapid rise of counter voltage and therefore reduction of current.

In applications with lower currents, natural commutation based on short arc voltage can be used for simplicity [9]. With higher currents it is necessary to use pre-charged capacitor C_h in order to overcome parasitics in the commutation loop [10].

The residual breaker is only required for electrical isolation and interrupts very low current with no need for fast operation. Although a mechanical switch, LC DC CB will not have any arcing except for very short (20-100 μs) commutating arc.

III. LC DC CB DESIGN

A. Ratings

It is decided to use 12 kV and 1 kA as initial nominal parameters which is expected to represent typical application in MV distribution or collection DC systems. The total operating time of around 2 ms should be achievable, considering performance of demonstrated HV DC CBs [4]. However since LC DC CB is able to commutate current in very short time, it is expected that the peak DC fault current may reach only 2-4 pu, which is much lower than values with commercial HV DC CBs of 16-25 kA [3],[4],[5], or MV DC CB [8]. All commercial DC CBs build counter voltage at the end of the stroke, while LC DC CB initiates counter voltage at the beginning of contact stroke.

Based on the above assumptions the following sections present essential design steps for all key DC CB components. The commercially available technology will be used where

possible, and conservative assumptions are adopted where technology is not available on the market.

B. Ultrafast Disconnecter

The 320 kV UFD used in the commercial hybrid DC CB [6] operates in around 2-3 ms [12]. This time is comparable with disconnectors and fast switches based on Thomson-coil drive, used in other commercial DC CBs [5].

The UFD design in [12] has numerous break points, which contribute to increase gap distance and separation velocity. It is assumed that 5-10 break points will be readily technically achievable with MV designs. UFD will normally have both rods driven with Thomson coils, and velocity of each rod has been measured at 2-10 m/s in practical designs [13].

The dielectric strength of gap media in UFD (d) is a critical parameter that determines performance and reliability of UFD and DC CB. Air will be assumed dielectric in the initial 12 kV UFD for simplicity. Considering theoretical value of 2 kV/mm, and a safety factor of 4, the assumed gap dielectric strength is $d_{air}=0.5$ kV/mm.

TABLE I. shows all assumed and calculated parameters.

C. Protection system

There are numerous DC protection algorithms, while manufacturers have announced their DC relays [14], and EU project PROMOTioN has demonstrated open source DC relay [15]. The demonstrated relay operation time is around 0.2 ms with some further delay possible depending on sensor response and communication.

The series inductor L_{dc} limits the current rise slope, which is required for DC protection discrimination and also helps reduce peak DC CB current. The basic design equation, conservatively assuming $V_{dc}=const$, is:

$$V_{dc}=L_{dc}(I_{cp}-I_o)/\Delta t \quad (1)$$

where Δt includes breaker and relay time, I_{cp} is current value at commutation and I_o is pre-fault (nominal) current. The calculated inductance is $L_{dc}=6$ mH, with the assumed $I_{cp}=4$ kA

Figure 1. LC DC CB and test circuit

and conservative values for delays as shown in TABLE I.

Figure 2. Shows time-domain fault-simulation with the test system parameters. The threshold for fault detection includes two conditions: 1) large voltage derivative $dV/dt < -3$ KV/ms, and 2) large current $I_{op} > 2$ kA.

TABLE I. TEST SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Disconnecter Parameters	Label, value, unit
Nominal voltage	$V_{dc} = 12$ kV
Nominal current	$I_o = 1$ kA
Rod velocity	$v_1 = 2.5$ m/s
Number of break points	$n = 6$
Dielectric strength	$d_{air} = 0.5$ kV/mm
Total gap velocity	$v_g = 6 * 2 * v_1 = 30$ m/s
Protection Parameters	
Series inductance	$L_{dc} = 6$ mH
Current threshold	$I_{op} = 2$ kA
Rate of voltage threshold	$dV/dt = -3$ kV/ms
Relay processing delay	0.5 ms
Time to contact separation	0.5 ms
Residual breaker opening time	9 ms
DC CB Parameters	
Current at commutation	$I_{cp} = 4$ kA
Main capacitance	$C_s = 250$ μ F (18 kV)
Pre-charged capacitance	$C_h = 6000$ μ F (0.84 kV)
Arrester	$V_{arr} = 18$ kV, $E_a = 210$ kJ
Fault resistance	$R_f = 5$ m Ω
Total parasitic inductance	$L_p = 4$ μ H
Total parasitic resistance	$R_p = 5$ m Ω

Figure 2. Simulation of protection system operation

D. Main capacitance C_s

The main capacitance C_s has significant impact on the performance, cost, size, and reliability of DC CB. Figure 3. shows the range of required C_s for different UFD rod velocity v_1 and commutating current I_{cp} . The initial value of $C_s = 250$ μ F is adopted.

E. Pre-charged circuit

The purpose of pre-charged capacitor C_h is to provide energy to aid current commutation from UFD to C_s . If there are

no parasitics, then current can commute naturally [9]. To minimize costs the voltage rating of V_{Ch} should be low, which is also voltage rating for trigger (T_t and D_t) and charging circuit. The capacitance C_h can be determined from the following:

$$C_h/C_s = V_{cs}/V_{ch} \quad (2)$$

The key requirement for the charging circuit is that the peak discharge current is larger than the commutating current. Figure 4. shows the simulation of C_h discharge with UFD closed and considering all parasitics as in 0It is seen that with the assumed $C_h = 6.8$ mF there will be 4 zero crossings, each having lower current derivative, and therefore good probability for current interruption in UFD.

The conservative values for parasitics are adopted by upscaling experimental values from [9] and [10].

Figure 3. Capacitance C_s versus commutating current I_{cp} .

IV. PRACTICAL DESIGN ASPECTS

An initial market search has been performed for the key DC CB components in order to evaluate feasibility and estimate size and weight. TABLE II. shows the main parameters.

G&W Electric is collaborating on the design and evaluation of the UFD. The initial assumptions and performance evaluation are considered technically feasible.

The arresters are readily available from multiple vendors.

The 18 kV film capacitor is custom made but feasible by multiple manufacturers, and will resemble technical characteristics of those at 6.5-10 kV described in detail [16].

The residual breaker is a standard AC single-phase switch. Operating speed is not important.

The series inductor is of cylindrical air-core design, made in-house according to design formula given in [3].

The pre-charged capacitor C_h can be of either film (safer) or electrolytic (less space) type, since there is no voltage V_{Ch} polarity change.

Figure 4. Design and testing of precharged-circuit ($C_h=6000 \mu F$)

TABLE II. KEY DCCB COMPONENTS

Component	Supplier	Dimension	Weight
Capacitor $C_s=250\mu F$, 18kV - estimate	Custom made	0.91x0.41x0.28m	80-100 kg
Arrester 4x $U_c=5kV$, $E_j=6.25 \text{ kJ/kV}$	Hitachi energy, POLIM-CN	0.115m x Φ 0.1m	4 x 1.6kg
UFD, 18 kV, 1kA, 2ms	G&W Electric	0.3x0.15x0.1	5-10kg
Residual breaker Trident SP, 15 kV load breaker	G&W Electric	1.19x0.4x0.7m	45kg
Series inductor $L_{dc}=6 \text{ mH}$ - estimate	Wound in house on cylindrical air-core	$\Phi=0.4 \text{ m}$, $l=216 \text{ m}$, $a=333 \text{ mm}^2$	644 kg.
Pre-charge capacitor (film)	EPCOS MKP-DC, 2x3400 μF , 0.9kV	$\Phi=136 \text{ mm}$, $l=304 \text{ mm}$,	2x 4.5 kg
Alternative Pre-charge capacitor (electrolytic)	KEMET Electrolytic 2x12 mF, 0.45kV	$\Phi=77 \text{ mm}$, $l=194 \text{ mm}$,	2x 1.4 kg

V. PSCAD SIMULATION

A PSCAD model of 12 kV DC CB is developed considering the modeling approach from [10]. The DC fault test circuit is simple and conservative as shown in Figure 1. , and all parameters are given in 0

Figure 5. shows the simulation responses for a DC fault at $0s$. The first 1 ms of the response is shown in more detail in Figure 2. In Figure 5. a) it is seen that:

- UFD current (I_{UFD}) peaks at 4 kA and drops to zero at commutation. The contact separation time of 0.5 ms is assumed [10][16], and signifies initiation of breaker counter voltage rise (and current reduction).

Figure 5. PSCAD testing of LC DC CB

- Capacitor current is 4 kA at commutation (at 0.5 ms) and peaks 4.7 kA at 1.7 ms after the trip signal,
- Arrester current peaks at 4.5 kA , and drops to zero 7 ms after the trip signal,
- I_{dc} has oscillating component which depends on the actual instant of S_2 opening, that cannot be predicted.

In Figure 5. b) it is seen that:

- Voltage V_{dccb} and voltage V_{Cs} peak at 17.8 kV ,
- Voltage V_{Ch} changes from -0.84 kV to final value of -0.05 kV at 3 ms , (no polarity change).
- Voltage V_{res} remains at 4 kV after opening S_2 , but this value depends on the actual instant of S_2 opening.

In Figure 5. c) it is seen that total energy dissipation is 220 kJ :

- Arrester SA_{Cs} energy dissipation is 210 kJ .
- Energy of capacitor C_s peaks at 40 kJ , but the final energy (10 kJ) depends on the instant of S_2 opening.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The design of a 12 kV , 1 kA LC DC Circuit Breaker is considered feasible, since fast disconnecter performance requirements are modest, and other key components are commercially available. The demonstrated performance indicators like operating time ($T_{cb}=2\text{ ms}$) and peak stresses ($I_{cp}=4\text{ kA}$) are found to be comparable or better than the existing commercial HV DC CBs. The largest component is the parallel capacitor with the calculated main parameters $V_{Cs}=18\text{ kV}$, $C_s=250\text{ }\mu\text{F}$, and estimated weight of $80\text{-}100\text{ kg}$. The estimated DC CB energy dissipation is 220 kJ , that can be accommodated with 4 standard 5 kV railway arresters, while C_s takes another 10 kJ . The weight for film pre-charged capacitor $C_{ch}=6\text{ mF}$, 0.8 kV is estimated at 9 kg , or if electrolytic type is used, weight is below 3 kg .

With all conservative assumptions, the total weight for 12 kV DC CB is expected to be $250\text{-}300\text{ kg}$ (including frame but without inductor), size of $1\times 1\times 0.5\text{ m}$, and the estimated performance is competitive.

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